

Sentinel-2 MSI imagery pre-processing strategy for improving chlorophyll-a monitoring at Ebro Delta bays (NW Mediterranean, Spain)

Abstract

Ebro Delta bays are two estuarine environments where phytoplankton (*i.e.* chlorophyll-a, chl-a), has a major importance because of shellfish aquaculture, which has a large socioeconomic impact in the region. The implementation of phytoplankton monitoring programs has become mandatory at European production sites and the use of space-borne remote sensing for this purpose has been increasing along the years. Quantitative remote sensing of chl allows the transformation of satellite images into chl-a distribution maps. Regular monitoring through space-borne sensors requires to estimate water-leaving radiance by removing atmospheric contributions from the signal received at the top of atmosphere (TOA) and to obtain a robust relationship between water quality and satellite-based parameters.

With the purpose of finding a suitable methodology for chl-a monitoring at Ebro Delta bays using space-borne remote sensing, this study aims to explore the performance of the Sentinel-2 multispectral instrument (S2/MSI) spectral bands and the derived spectral indices for chl-a retrieval. The proposed approach uses both TOA and bottom of atmosphere (BOA) images together with several pre-processing technics including different atmospheric processors, pixels outlier detection, principal component analysis (PCA) and spectral separability study. Thus, the objectives are;

- 1) Assessing the spectral differences between atmospherically uncorrected and corrected images comparing different atmosphere correction processors;
- 2) Finding the maximum or optimum size of the pixel window that could be used for model calibration (spatially average the reflectance over a number of pixels centered at an in situ measurement site for reducing environmental, sensor and positioning noises) and
- 3) Determinate the sensivity of the different bands and spectral indices to quantify chl-a at different concentrations (for band selection and algorithm building).

Similar approaches have been proposed for inland waters, but the use of Sentinel-2 is still scarce when assessing coastal areas. In addition, the use of space-borne remote sensing is commonly used to derive site-and-time specific empirical algorithms (regional tuning). Here, the proposed methodology has been tested with 42 Sentinel-2 images covering all the year 2017, and thus including several environmental scenarios. The S2 imagery were atmospherically corrected with both ACOLITE and POLYMER processors. On this time-series, several spectral indices were computed and S2/MSI full spectrum was considered. Pixel intra-stability was evaluated by the use of the coefficient of variation (Cv) and pixel inter-variability was analysed by means of spectral separability. For all indices two different models were developed by using two in-situ measures of chl-a (Nfluorimeter = 56 and Nspectrophotomete = 43), all S2/MSI bands were considered in a PCA for new algorithm development.

The results of our study show that despite not being designed for aquatic purposes, Sentinel-2 satellites provide a new opportunity for moderate spatial resolution of chlorophyll-a (chl-a) retrieval, mapping and monitoring at coastal areas. The preliminary results, in agreement with the ones obtained in other coastal areas, suggest the need for atmospheric correction processing. The CV served as an outlier detector and the PCA and spectral separability analyses provided for the best configuration of the methodology (bands used, spectral indices and average pixel window size).